

THE EFFECT OF SURFACE MODIFICATION ON INTERFACE OF POLYKETONE FIBER AND RUBBER

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1 Introduction

Worldwide demand for super fibers is on increase, in order to satisfy requirements of various functional fabrics. Because of this tendency, super fibers have higher tensile strength and modulus and also, provide the energy savings and safety applications [1]. Each super fiber has specific characteristics. Among these, polyketone fiber has higher strength, chemical resistance, abrasion resistance and hydrolysis resistance than para-aramid and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) [2]. Polyketone fiber is available by copolymerization of carbon monoxide and unsaturated hydrocarbon monomer, ethylene. This fiber may also have the added benefit of a lower price compared with other super fiber. It is expected to apply polyketone to tires, hoses and protective gloves [3]. The purpose of this study was to improve the interfacial property between polyketone fiber and rubber. The tensile strength and modulus, FT-IR, XPS, SEM and AFM is used to evaluate the effect of UV irradiation and acid treatment on mechanical, chemical and morphological properties. Additionally, pull-out test is performed to evaluate the interfacial shear strength.

2 Experimental

2.1 Material

The molecular structure of polyketone fiber is shown in figure 1. The polyketone fiber in this study was supplied from Hyosung Corp. Korea. The average linear mass density of fiber is 747denier.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of polyketone

2.2 Surface Modification

Polyketone fibers were cleaned with acetone by ultrasonic agitation for 1h. Then, the polyketone fibers were washed with distilled water repeatedly. After purifying polyketone fiber, it was irradiated by UV with the energy of 10, 20, 30 and 40 kJ and treated with phosphoric acid with 20 wt.% (pH 0.74) and 40 wt.% (pH 0.4) for 30, 60, 120 and 240min at 40°C.

2.3 Mechanical properties

Single fiber tensile property tests were performed on the conditioned specimens in the standard atmosphere. Single fiber tensile strength and modulus were measured with an Instron 4467 according to ASTM D 3822-7 using a gauge length of 25mm and a cross-head speed of 5mm/min.

2.4 Chemical properties

A Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (Bruker Optic GmbH, ALPHA-P) equipped with an ATR accessory was used. The spectra were recorded in the transmission mode in the range 4000-500 cm^{-1} . FT-IR spectra were measured at a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , and the spectra were obtained with an accumulation of 128 scans for a high signal-to-noise ratio. The surface element and functional group analysis of polyketone fiber were performed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, Multilab 2000, Thermo) equipped with a Mg-K α , X-ray source.

2.5 Morphological properties

SEM images of polyketone fibers were observed before and after treatments and compared to those of raw fiber. Additionally, AFM were investigated to measure the three dimensional images of polyketone fibers and root mean square (RMS) roughness data, which were obtained by analyzing topography images.

2.6 Interfacial shear strength

The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) between the polyketone fibers and rubber was measured by the micro-bond test using an Instron test system (model 4467) equipped with 500N load cell. Tests were performed at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min. Tests were carried out at room temperature. The maximum force (F_{max}) was recorded to calculate the maximum interfacial shear strength (τ_{max}) using equation (1):

$$\tau_{max} = F_{max} / \pi DL \quad (1)$$

Where, D and L are fiber diameter and droplet diameter, respectively.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Mechanical properties

The monofilament tensile strength and modulus were not changed significantly by UV irradiation and acid treatment. However, the mechanical properties were decreased with severe treat such as 40wt.% for 240min.

3.2 Chemical properties

According to FT-IR and XPS results, the oxygen containing functional groups such as hydroxyl, carbonyl and carboxyl were increased. The change of the surface chemical composition could result from the etching of the oxidized fiber surface.

3.3 Morphological properties

The UV irradiated and acid treated polyketone fibers showed micro-pores and cracks on the fiber surface compared with untreated fibers. The size and number of micro-pore and cracks increased slightly as the UV energy increased and as phosphoric acid concentration and treatment time increased. Therefore, the surface roughness was increased because of generated micro-pores and cracks.

3.3 Interfacial shear strength

The IFSS between polyketone fibers and rubber was determined by measuring the micro-bond test. The IFSS of fibers irradiated by UV and treated by phosphoric acid was much higher than that of untreated fiber. The IFSS was increased with increase of surface roughness as UV energy, phosphoric acid concentration and treatment time increased which leading to increased mechanical interlocking area.

4 Conclusions

Polyketone fibers were irradiated by UV and treated with phosphoric acid in order to improve the interfacial shear strength of fiber and rubber. The surface chemical and morphological properties were changed by UV irradiation and acid treatment. Consequently, the adhesion property was increased due to the creation of micro-pores and cracks.

Acknowledgement

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